

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: Creativity and innovation are essential components of teaching and learning, notably in the social sciences. Creativity and originality pique the attention and motivation of English learners and English teacher-trainees, which leads to learning.

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Creativity and innovation are essential components of teaching and learning, notably in the social sciences. Creativity and originality pique the attention and motivation of English learners and English teacher-trainees, which leads to learning. The days of a Professor delivering a lecture while standing behind a rostrum in a huge lecture hall in a one-way communication mode where his/her words are words of God, and students sit quietly embracing his/her words, busy taking notes, are long gone, and they have been replaced with more innovative and creative ways of disseminating, sharing, and facilitating knowledge development in students have long passed. Our students are tired of the old school approach to learning a language – they want something practical, relevant and useful for their professional life. With computer being their flesh and blood; and living in the era where they are allowed to question on things and they are empowered to be partly responsible for their learning, creativity and innovation have been incorporated in my teaching and learning, assessment and supervision.

To build relationships with our students and help them learn the English language, be creative, understanding, and encouraging. It goes against traditional teaching's tried-and-true comfort zone to use task-based learning to teach English.

Why is creative approach important in teaching?

Creative thinking in classrooms alters the way students approach a problem. It allows them to think outside the box, experiment and come up with innovative ways to find solutions for various problems. Improves communication skills: A classroom that fosters creativity improves students' communication skills.

What is creative approaches in teaching?

Creative approaches are concerned with a holistic approach to education, focusing upon the learner becoming part of a professional community, involving the dimensions of knowledge, performance and identity formation.

What is the importance of teaching creativity to children?

Importance of the Creative Process

A child's creative activity can help teachers to learn more about what the child may be thinking or feeling. Creativity also fosters mental growth in children by providing opportunities for trying out new ideas, and new ways of thinking and problem-solving.

What are the benefits of creativity?

Here are 5 benefits of expressing yourself creatively – along with a jam-packed list of how you can do that.

- Creativity improves your mood. ...
- Creativity boosts your self-esteem. ...
- Creativity improves cognitive function. ...
- Creativity improves your social life. ...
- Creativity alleviates stress and anxiety.

Strategies adopted to stimulate and foster higher thinking skills (HOTS)

At tertiary level of education, students should be independent and empowered to be responsible for their own learning. Spoon-feeding approach should never be practiced at all. To develop the skill of high level thinking, responsibilities for learning should be shifted to them through approaches such as problem-based learning (PBL) where students play a major role in learning the new topic and this knowledge is later shared with those who may not have the opportunity to work on that topic yet. Through PBL, not only the students become self-directed learners; they are also taught responsibilities, decision-making skills, leadership skills.

Exploratory learning is yet another way of instilling high level thinking. This is because, through exploration learners will be required to piece together the pieces of the jigsaw puzzle of all new information so as to be able to make sense of the new discovery, making the brains remaining active all the time.

Bringing innovation and creativity to the language classroom is like introducing a new toy to a toddler. The chalk and talk approach to teaching and learning is something that they have grown so accustomed to that anything, just about anything new is welcomed by the learners.

Cooperative learning may be thought of as something that students dread doing as the process and the product will force them to communicate in the target language. Surprisingly, the cooperative learning I adopt in my classroom brings about more interest and motivation for them to participate. In fact some even suggested and expressed that this approach of language learning is what they have been missing all these years.

Exploratory learning – One of the topics in my CALL I course is the incorporation of MSWord tools in teaching and learning. One of the in-class activities that I do in this class is to get the students to explore the tools available in MS Word and for them to brainstorm among themselves on the relevance of these tools in their language classroom.

Discovery learning – One of the effects of bringing innovation and creativity into the classroom is I instill the passion for discovering and testing out new things. The following is an example of how my students, after being exposed to the author ware HotPotatoes, go beyond the minimum knowledge of using the software.

Teaching Frame

Seeking to adapt the best methodology for my purposes, I needed to have a grasp of the course content as well as access to all necessary materials, including screenplays, creative writing exercises, and other resources. I intended not to go over the same content that students were learning. I took a broader view, considering the ideas and assumptions behind the content and anticipating topics that students would be studying.

I systematized this pedagogical experience by following the tenets of action research, an approach that could be a huge step toward making the positive changes in the English class that my creative activities are meant to achieve. This process is related to Carr and Kemmis (1986), who contend that action research helps teachers make changes in carrying out their classroom practices and in planning, implementing, and evaluating them. My activities are intended to be implemented and reflected upon according to the data gathered from participants.

Kemmis and McTaggart (1988) add that action research means to plan, act, observe, and reflect more carefully, more systematically, and more rigorously than one usually does in everyday life. Though I present this article as a pedagogical experience, I see action research as paramount in systematically collecting the data that help me organize my thoughts in planning and carrying out classroom activities. In the last fifteen years, teachers and educators have increasingly relied on action research methodology to collect reliable data and provide valuable insights to classroom teachers, and it has proven to be an excellent source of archival data (Zuber-Skerritt, 1991).

In carrying out classroom activities, I used Elliot's (1991) action model, in which the teacher plans, acts, observes, and reflects upon the pedagogical experience. This cycle includes the planning of exercises and pertinent observation as the teacher helps students improve their oral and written production skills and increases their motivation to learn. Observing, acting, and reflecting on these activities create a proper space for a pedagogical experience to take place and for students to communicate their feelings and enhance their abilities in the target language.

Several activities were planned according to the time I had with the participants. The purpose was to introduce students to creative methods supported by theory. In the workshops carried out in this teaching experience, students found exercises that led their language skills in various directions, as well as strategic steps with which to use their knowledge. Besides that, students found techniques to support their views in order to have a solid foundation in their foreign language practice.

The exercises were created to let students write/speak with focus and direction, to develop their ideas and descriptions, to discover their voices, and to apply grammar rules in a fun way. I consider my activities such as chain games and teamwork to comprise a great space for students to communicate their feelings through exercises so as to develop their thinking and enhance their abilities in the target language. My intention was to design activities that offered students the opportunity to communicate their feelings, develop their thinking, and enhance their abilities in the target language. Thus, participants were given an opportunity to develop their creative potential and to synthesize and apply knowledge and skills by creating and participating in the teaching process.

Peers' and public's response to innovation and creativity

One of the components of the CALL I course is software review and evaluation where students are exposed to the skills of reviewing and evaluating software

before deciding to adopt and adapt it for classroom teaching and learning. In addition, they are required to propose the use of the content of the software reviewed in a particular KBSM lesson. With the enormous number of software flooding the market today, teachers of English may be spoiled for choice, but through the skill learned, I have turned what is supposedly a straight forward activity into something which can be used by the masses as whatever id reviewed and evaluated is compiled into a CD and each member of the class will get a copy so that they could adopt what is suggested or they could share this with other fellow teachers in their schools in future.

Conclusion

While giving instruction on creativity is a huge difficulty and a high priority for future course design for students, researchers have focused their attention on establishing ways to improve student creativity. The purpose of this study is to suggest and investigate if and how numerous mechanisms can moderate the influence of a creative learning environment on undergraduate creativity. According to the findings of the study, a creative learning environment may considerably improve students' learning goal orientation, network links, and information sharing, hence facilitating their creativity. Researchers and educators should be more concerned with creating creative learning settings and assisting students in developing a learning goal orientation, network links, and information sharing.

References:

1. https://www-scielo-org.co.translate.googleusercontent.com/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S012059272015000200006&x_tr_sch=http&x_tr_sl=en&x_tr_tl=uz&x_tr_hl=uz&x_tr_pto=sc
2. https://link-springer-com.translate.googleusercontent.com/article/10.1007/s12144-020-00974-z?error=cookies_not_supported&code=6324c0fd-059c-4f75-83fe-53dca4a0139d&x_tr_sl=en&x_tr_tl=uz&x_tr_hl=uz&x_tr_pto=sc
3. Amabile, T. M. (1996). Creativity and innovation in organizations. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.